

Native Fixed NH_4^+ and the Fixation of Applied NH_4^+ in Some Soils of West Bengal

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The soils of West Bengal contain an appreciable proportion of native fixed NH_4^+ and the values range from 114 to 554 ppm which contribute 59.7 to 93.6% of the mineral nitrogen of the soils. Significant correlation exists between native fixed ammonium and clay, C.E.C., total nitrogen and inorganic nitrogen of the soils. Fixation of added NH_4^+ increases with the increase of the concentration and with the increase of the pH of the soil fixation also increases but from pH 7 the fixation is practically constant. Amount of clay and C.E.C. of the soils are important factors which affect the fixation of added NH_4^+ .

AVAILABLE evidence indicates that a considerable amount of soil nitrogen exists in the form of native fixed ammonium¹⁻³. However, its proportion varies with the nature and characteristics of the soils. Per cent clay, nature of clay minerals, exchangeable potassium, amount of organic matter and cation exchange capacity⁴⁻¹⁰ are the most important characteristics affecting the content of fixed ammonium in soils. Not much data on native fixed NH_4^+ and relative distribution of other forms of nitrogen are available for soils of West Bengal. The present work has, therefore, been undertaken to study the distribution of different forms of nitrogen in some soils of different agroclimatic regions of West Bengal. The present work also deals with the study on the factors affecting the fixation of added NH_4^+ in different soils.

Experimental

Soil samples were collected (0-15 cm) from 15 different regions of West Bengal. The soils were dried under shade, ground and passed through 80 mesh sieve. The relevant characteristics of the soils are given in table 1.

Native fixed NH_4^+ was determined by the method of Silva and Bremner¹¹. Available nitrogen (soluble $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ +exchangeable $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ + $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$) was estimated by the method as described by Jackson¹². Total nitrogen was analysed by Kjeldahl method. The amount of organic nitrogen present was calculated by subtracting inorganic nitrogen (sum of the values of soluble NH_4^+ , exchangeable NH_4^+ , $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ and native fixed NH_4^+) from total nitrogen.

TABLE I—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SOILS

Soil	Predominant clay minerals	pH (1:2.5 ratio)	Clay (%)	Silt (%)	Sand (%)	Organic Carbon (%)	C.E.C. me/100 gm	Av. N. (ppm)	Total N (%)	Native fixed NH_4^+ (ppm)
Kalimpong	Illite	4.5	12.7	20.6	65.7	0.98	10.6	35.1	0.07	145
Mangpo	"	4.8	10.5	22.8	66.7	1.59	10.5	45.6	0.14	141
Alipurduar	"	4.8	24.9	26.7	48.0	1.62	8.7	118.6	0.09	176
Purbasthali	"	4.8	80.9	18.6	2.1	1.07	41.7	39.2	0.14	554
Jhargram	Kaolinite	5.3	22.5	21.0	56.7	0.30	8.6	10.2	0.04	149
Santiniketan	"	5.9	11.5	7.0	75.0	0.30	3.4	30.2	0.03	114
Bishnupur	"	6.0	14.5	12.0	73.5	0.38	5.9	35.0	0.05	145
Sriniketan	"	6.2	17.6	3.3	79.1	0.29	7.9	24.6	0.03	161
Canning	Illite	6.4	42.1	43.2	14.7	0.81	18.6	35.0	0.09	212
Kalyani	"	6.7	47.0	23.5	26.5	1.08	32.4	31.0	0.14	339
Baidyanathpur	"	6.8	31.0	34.6	35.6	1.12	14.4	31.6	0.09	454
Baksha	"	6.8	56.5	32.5	10.7	0.82	19.8	25.7	0.11	292
Baliapur	"	6.9	38.3	37.3	23.9	0.75	16.7	40.6	0.08	395
Chinsurah	"	7.1	54.2	28.1	17.7	0.96	33.5	26.0	0.09	297
Purulia	Kaolinite	7.3	22.2	18.2	59.6	0.30	7.2	24.6	0.03	162

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All other characteristics of the soils were determined by the methods as described by Jackson (loc. cit.).

Effect of different concentrations of added NH_4^+ on the fixation process

In this experiment 10 g of each soil in duplicate were taken in glass tubes and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ solution @ 50, 100, 150 and 200 ppm of N were added and incubated in moist condition for 15 and 30 days at 25°. The amount of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ fixed in 15 and 30 days were estimated by Silva and Bremner method (loc.cit.).

Effect of pH on ammonium fixation

In this experiment soils of Santiniketan and Kalyani were used. The soils were treated separately with varying amounts of N/20 HCl and saturated $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ solution so as to obtain soils of different pH's and incubated with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ (100 ppm of N) in moist condition for 15 days at 25°. Control was run simultaneously. After 15 days, pH of the soils and amount of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ fixed were determined as usual.

Results and Discussion

The results presented in table 1 indicate that all the soils contain an appreciable amount of native fixed NH_4^+ and the values range from 114 to 554 ppm. Soils of Purbasthali, Baidyanathpur, Baliapur, Canning, Chinsurah and Kalyani, all of alluvial origin, contain higher amount of native fixed NH_4^+ . This can be attributed to the presence of illitic types of clay minerals in these soils. On the otherhand, in red and lateritic soils (Purulia, Santiniketan, Sriniketan, Jhargram and Bishnupur), the native fixed NH_4^+ present is comparatively low which is attributed to the kaolinite type of clay minerals present in these soils.

NH_4^+ than Mongpoo and Kalimpong soils though the first two are rich in kaolinite and the latter are rich in illite. Again, the soils of Purulia, Sriniketan, Santiniketan and Jhargram contain same amount of organic matter and the dominant clay mineral present in them is kaolinite but the amount of clay present in them is different and the quantity of the native fixed NH_4^+ varies. It is evident from the table 1 that higher the clay content the greater is the amount of native fixed NH_4^+ in these soils. The same sequence is observed in the soils of Purbasthali and Kalyani. These soils contain same amount of organic matter and the dominant clay mineral present is illite but they differ in clay content. Purbasthali soil contains higher amount of clay (80.9%) than Kalyani soil (47.0%) and the native fixed NH_4^+ in Purbasthali soil is high. In the soils of Canning and Baksha the same thing is observed. Therefore, it can be said that the amount of clay is an important factor which affects the content of native fixed NH_4^+ in soils. This is verified from the statistical analysis. Native fixed NH_4^+ gives a highly significant positive correlation ($r = 0.7875^{**}$) with the clay content of the soils.

Cation exchange capacity is also another factor which affects the content of fixed NH_4^+ in soils. Correlation between native fixed NH_4^+ and c.E.c. of the soils is highly significant ($r = 0.8698^{**}$).

Table 2 reveals that native fixed NH_4^+ contributes substantially to total nitrogen. This as a fraction of total nitrogen varies from 10.07 to 54.00%. Corresponding values reported by Raju and Mukherje¹³ are 4.9 to 54.0% for some soils of West Bengal. Native fixed NH_4^+ , on the otherhand, is accounted for most of the mineral nitrogen of the

TABLE 2.—DISTRIBUTION OF DIFFERENT FORMS OF NITROGEN

Soil	Total inorganic nitrogen (ppm)	Total organic nitrogen (ppm)	Native fixed NH_4^+ as a fraction of total nitrogen (%)	Native fixed NH_4^+ as a fraction of inorganic nitrogen (%)	Inorganic nitrogen as a fraction of total nitrogen (%)	Organic C / Organic N	Organic C / Total N
Kalimpong	180.1	519.9	20.70	80.5	25.7	18.9	14.0
Mongpoo	186.6	1213.4	10.07	75.5	13.3	13.2	11.3
Alipurduar	294.6	605.4	19.55	59.7	32.7	27.0	18.0
Purbasthali	593.2	806.8	39.57	93.4	42.3	13.4	7.6
Jhargram	159.2	240.8	37.25	93.6	39.8	15.5	7.7
Santiniketan	144.2	155.8	38.00	79.0	48.0	20.0	10.0
Bishnupur	180.0	320.0	29.00	80.5	36.0	12.7	7.6
Sriniketan	185.6	114.4	53.66	86.7	61.8	26.3	9.7
Canning	247.0	653.0	23.55	85.8	27.4	12.5	9.0
Kalyani	370.0	1030.0	24.21	91.6	26.4	10.8	7.7
Baidyanathpur	485.6	414.4	50.44	93.4	53.9	28.0	12.4
Baksha	317.7	782.3	26.54	91.9	28.8	10.5	7.5
Baliapur	435.6	364.4	49.37	90.6	54.4	20.8	9.4
Chinsurah	253.0	647.0	25.22	89.7	28.1	14.7	10.7
Purulia	186.6	113.4	54.00	86.8	62.2	27.3	10.0

But table 1 shows that the clay mineral is not the only factor for the differential amount of the native fixed NH_4^+ present in the soils. Purulia and Sriniketan soils contain higher amount of native fixed

soils and varies from 59.7 to 93.6%. This is quite expected because the amount of available nitrogen present in the soils studied is very low. Table 2 also reveals that organic C/organic N values of all the

soils are higher than organic C/total N values. This indicates that inorganic nitrogen constitutes a considerable part of total N which is also supported from the data given in column 5 of the Table 2. The value varies from 13.3 to 62.2%.

Correlation coefficient values indicate that native fixed NH_4^+ is significantly correlated with inorganic nitrogen ($r = 9963^{**}$) as well as total nitrogen ($r = 0.579^*$) whereas it does not bear any significant relationship with organic carbon ($r = 0.3005$).

The data on the effect of different concentrations of ammonium sulphate on the fixation of NH_4^+ are given in table 3. Table shows that in all the soils

results but at high concentration the curve flattens out indicating that at low concentration NH_4^+ fixation is an adsorption phenomenon.

Table 3 also reveals that the fixation does not increase so much when the incubation period is increased from 15 to 30 days. This indicates that ammonium fixation is a rapid process and maximum fixation occurs within 15 days. The high rate observed at initial stage is probably due to the fact that the fixation proceeds from surface and edge to the interior of the particle.

The fixation of added NH_4^+ does not bear any definite analogy with the carbon content of the soil.

TABLE 3—FIXATION OF $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ (PPM)* FROM THE ADDED $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$

Soil	15 days' incubation				30 days' incubation			
	Treatments				Treatments			
	50 ppm	100 ppm	150 ppm	200 ppm	50 ppm	100 ppm	150 ppm	200 ppm
Kalimpong	20.0	29.8	42.6	58.5	22.8	32.5	45.9	61.6
Mongpoo	18.1	25.3	41.6	58.5	23.2	30.1	50.5	67.3
Alipurduar	26.5	41.2	60.3	76.2	30.1	44.8	67.1	79.8
Purbasthali	40.0	63.0	80.9	99.0	42.9	68.3	85.0	110.6
Jhargram	25.2	39.8	52.6	60.5	27.9	42.6	58.9	66.2
Santiniketan	15.7	23.4	30.8	40.0	20.2	28.2	32.8	45.8
Bishnupur	15.8	26.5	40.0	55.1	18.1	28.1	45.2	60.2
Sriniketan	19.6	38.2	50.6	61.2	26.0	40.2	56.8	65.1
Canning	28.6	42.0	66.7	88.2	33.8	46.8	68.4	91.7
Kalyani	34.1	51.2	64.8	96.0	38.9	53.6	70.1	104.1
Baidyanathpur	26.4	46.7	53.3	72.2	27.1	50.6	55.6	80.5
Baksha	33.2	54.5	68.5	91.2	36.6	59.8	73.1	95.6
Balipur	27.1	50.5	68.5	92.6	30.6	52.9	80.9	96.4
Chinsurah	32.2	50.2	71.3	95.6	36.0	58.4	75.2	102.8
Purulia	19.2	30.6	48.0	58.6	24.0	36.8	56.2	60.0
Mean values	25.4	41.1	56.0	78.1	29.2	45.5	61.4	79.4

* Average of duplicate determinations which were almost identical.

the amount fixed increases with the increase of the concentration of ammonium sulphate solution. Allison¹⁴ explained this by suggesting the existence of equilibrium between three forms of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$:

Since with the successive addition of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ the amount of available $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ is always increased, the fixation will be increased upto a certain limit.

In order to see whether the ammonium fixation in soil follows the adsorption phenomenon, the mean values of the amount of NH_4^+ fixed in 15 and 30 days to all soils after addition of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ are calculated. Now equilibrium concentration is plotted against equilibrium concentration ($C/\frac{x}{m}$ against C). The figure shows that at lower concentration a straight line

It is found that some soils (Mongpoo and Alipurduar) containing higher amount of organic carbon fix a small quantity whereas the soils (Baksha and Kalyani) having comparatively lesser amount have the higher fixation capacity although all of them contain illite types of clay minerals. Mean value of the fixed NH_4^+ at four different concentrations of each soil bears a significant positive correlation with the clay content ($r = 0.9368^{**}$) and c.e.c. ($r = 0.8698^{**}$) of the soils. This indicates that fixation of added NH_4^+ also depends on the clay content and c.e.c. of the soils.

Table 4 shows that pH is also an important factor in NH_4^+ fixation. Acidification of soils markedly reduces the fixation capacity while with the increase of pH of the soils by the addition of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, the fixation capacity increases. This observation is in the line with that made by Karim and Malek¹⁵ and Shoji and Mastumi¹⁶.

Table 4 also shows that though the fixation increases with the increase in pH, the amount fixed is practically constant from pH near about 7.0. It is

 TABLE 4—EFFECT OF pH ON THE FIXATION OF ADDED NH_4^+

Kalyani Soil		Santiniketan Soil	
pH	Fixed $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ (ppm)	pH	Fixed $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ (ppm)
4.00	2.0	4.00	Trace
4.45	12.4	4.50	"
4.80	20.4	4.90	4.0
5.95	31.0	5.20	15.6
6.70	50.2	5.50	23.8
6.80	51.2	5.80	26.8
7.00	51.5	6.65	31.1
7.30	52.0	6.80	32.2
7.50	53.0	7.30	33.1
—	—	7.40	34.5

also evident that pH level round about 6.7-7.0 is most favourable for the maximum fixation for both the soils having different clay contents and different clay minerals. Further studies are in progress in this regard for drawing definite conclusions.

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